

A Prospective Study to Evaluate Changes in Macular Thickness after uncomplicated cataract Surgery Using OCT in Diabetic Patients

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Abstract:

Background: Cataract surgery is a common procedure that can pose significant risks in diabetic patients, particularly related to the development of macular edema. Monitoring changes in macular thickness postoperatively is crucial for managing these risks effectively.

Aim: To evaluate the changes in macular thickness in diabetic patients after uncomplicated cataract surgery using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and to assess the impact of glycemic control on these changes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted, involving 100 diabetic patients who underwent uncomplicated cataract surgery. Macular thickness was measured using OCT preoperatively, and at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months postoperatively. The relationship between glycemic control, as indicated by HbA1c levels, and changes in macular thickness was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean preoperative macular thickness was $270.5 \pm 18.4 \mu\text{m}$, which increased significantly to $282.3 \pm 20.2 \mu\text{m}$ at 1 week postoperatively ($p < 0.001$) and gradually decreased to $271.8 \pm 17.9 \mu\text{m}$ by 3 months ($p = 0.254$). A moderate positive correlation was found between HbA1c levels and the increase in macular thickness at 1 week ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$). Visual acuity improved significantly from $0.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ logMAR}$ preoperatively to $0.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ logMAR}$ at 3 months postoperatively ($p < 0.001$). The incidence of clinically significant macular edema (CSME) decreased from 15% at 1 week to 3% at 3 months.

Conclusion: Diabetic patients with uncomplicated cataract surgery experience a temporary increase in macular thickness that disappears within 3 months. Postoperative macular thickening increases with poor glycaemic management. Proper surgical care improves visual outcomes despite the temporary retinal thickness increase.

Recommendations: Clinicians should closely monitor macular thickness in diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery, particularly in those with poor glycemic control. Further research is recommended to explore preventive measures for macular edema in this high-risk population.

Keywords: Cataract Surgery, Diabetic Patients, Macular Thickness, Optical Coherence Tomography, Glycemic Control.

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Introduction

Cataract surgery is one of the most commonly performed ophthalmic procedures worldwide and is generally regarded as safe and effective in restoring vision. However, in diabetic patients, the procedure carries a higher risk of postoperative complications, particularly related to the macula. Diabetic retinopathy (DR), a common microvascular complication of diabetes, often leads to macular edema, which can be exacerbated by cataract surgery. The pathophysiology involves increased vascular permeability and fluid accumulation in the macula, potentially leading to a significant decline in visual acuity if not properly managed [1].

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) has revolutionized the ability to monitor and measure

macular thickness, providing a non-invasive and highly sensitive method for detecting changes in the retinal layers. This is particularly important in diabetic patients, where subtle changes in macular thickness can signal the early onset of complications such as diabetic macular edema (DME). Recent studies have highlighted the importance of monitoring macular thickness before and after cataract surgery in diabetic patients to identify those at risk of developing significant postoperative edema [2].

Research conducted over the past few years has focused on the incidence and management of macular thickening after cataract surgery in diabetic patients. A study demonstrated that

diabetic patients are more likely to experience an increase in macular thickness following uncomplicated cataract surgery compared to non-diabetic individuals [3]. The transient nature of this thickening suggests that while it is a common occurrence, it does not necessarily lead to long-term visual impairment if appropriately managed. Another study found that the extent of postoperative macular thickening was directly correlated with the level of glycemic control, as measured by HbA1c [4]. This emphasizes the role of systemic diabetes management in optimizing surgical outcomes.

Despite these advances, there remains variability in the reported incidence of postoperative macular thickening, likely due to differences in study populations, surgical techniques, and definitions of clinically significant macular edema (CSME).

This study aims to evaluate changes in macular thickness after uncomplicated cataract surgery in diabetic patients using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT).

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a duration of 22 months at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur.

Participants: A total of 100 diabetic patients who underwent uncomplicated cataract surgery were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adult diabetic patients aged 40 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with cataracts and scheduled for uncomplicated cataract surgery.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients with stable glycemic control (HbA1c $\leq$ 7.5%).

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of macular disease such as diabetic macular edema or age-related macular degeneration.
- Patients with a history of previous intraocular surgery.

- Patients with any other ocular pathology that could affect macular thickness.
- Patients who experienced complications during cataract surgery.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were consecutively recruited based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Observer bias was reduced by ensuring that the same ophthalmologist performed all OCT measurements and the analysis was conducted in a blinded manner.

Data Collection: Data was collected through preoperative and postoperative evaluations. Preoperative assessments included a detailed ocular examination, measurement of macular thickness using OCT, and recording of demographic data, medical history, and glycemic control. Postoperative follow-up was conducted at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months, with macular thickness measured using OCT at each visit.

Procedure: Uncomplicated cataract surgery was performed on all participants by a skilled ophthalmologist using phacoemulsification technique under local anesthesia. Standard postoperative care was provided, and participants were followed up as per the study protocol. OCT scans were conducted preoperatively and during each follow-up visit to measure changes in macular thickness.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Paired t-tests were conducted to compare preoperative and postoperative macular thickness measurements. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Additionally, correlation analyses were performed to assess the relationship between changes in macular thickness and glycemic control.

Result

A total of 100 diabetic patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 62.3 ± 7.5 years. The study population consisted of 52 males and 48 females. The average duration of diabetes was 12.6 ± 5.2 years, and the mean HbA1c level was $7.2\% \pm 0.3\%$. All participants underwent uncomplicated cataract surgery, and no intraoperative complications were reported.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	100
Mean Age (years)	62.3 ± 7.5
Gender (M/F)	52/48
Duration of Diabetes (years)	12.6 ± 5.2
Mean HbA1c (%)	7.2 ± 0.3

The mean preoperative macular thickness was $270.5 \pm 18.4 \mu\text{m}$. Postoperatively, the macular thickness was measured at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months. At 1 week, the mean macular thickness increased to $282.3 \pm 20.2 \mu\text{m}$, representing a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.001$). At 1 month, the mean macular thickness was $278.1 \pm$

$19.1 \mu\text{m}$, which was still significantly higher than the preoperative value ($p < 0.05$). However, by 3 months, the mean macular thickness had returned to near preoperative levels, measuring $271.8 \pm 17.9 \mu\text{m}$, with no statistically significant difference from the preoperative value ($p = 0.254$).

Table 2: Macular Thickness Measurements at Different Time Points

Time Point	Mean Macular Thickness (μm)	p-value
Preoperative	270.5 ± 18.4	-
1 Week Postoperative	282.3 ± 20.2	< 0.001
1 Month Postoperative	278.1 ± 19.1	< 0.05
3 Months Postoperative	271.8 ± 17.9	0.254

A correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationship between HbA1c levels and changes in macular thickness at 1 week and 1 month postoperatively. The analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between HbA1c levels and the increase in macular thickness at 1 week ($r = 0.42$, p

< 0.001). At 1 month, the correlation was weaker but still significant ($r = 0.30$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that poorer glycemic control was associated with a greater increase in macular thickness postoperatively.

Table 3: Correlation Between HbA1c Levels and Change in Macular Thickness

Time Point	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
1 Week Postoperative	0.42	< 0.001
1 Month Postoperative	0.30	< 0.05

Clinically significant macular edema (CSME) was defined as an increase in macular thickness of more than $30 \mu\text{m}$ from the preoperative value. At 1 week, 15 patients (15%) developed CSME. By 1 month, the number of patients with CSME decreased to 8

(8%), and by 3 months, only 3 patients (3%) had persistent CSME. These results indicate a transient increase in macular thickness postoperatively, with most cases resolving by 3 months.

Table 4: Incidence of Clinically Significant Macular Edema

Time Point	Number of Patients with CSME	Percentage (%)
1 Week Postoperative	15	15%
1 Month Postoperative	8	8%
3 Months Postoperative	3	3%

Visual acuity was assessed preoperatively and at each postoperative visit. The mean best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) improved from $0.6 \pm 0.2 \log\text{MAR}$ preoperatively to $0.3 \pm 0.1 \log\text{MAR}$ at 3 months postoperatively ($p < 0.001$). The improvement in visual acuity was observed in all patients, regardless of changes in macular thickness.

Table 5: Visual Acuity Outcomes (BCVA in logMAR)

Time Point	Mean BCVA (logMAR)	p-value
Preoperative	0.6 ± 0.2	-
3 Months Postoperative	0.3 ± 0.1	< 0.001

Discussion

The results of this prospective observational study indicate that uncomplicated cataract surgery in diabetic patients is associated with a transient increase in macular thickness, as measured by Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). The macular thickness significantly increased during the first postoperative week, with a peak at one week and a gradual reduction by three months post-surgery, at which point it approached preoperative levels. This transient thickening suggests that while cataract surgery may initially exacerbate macular

edema in diabetic patients, the effects are largely temporary, with most patients experiencing resolution of the edema within three months.

The study also found a significant correlation between glycemic control, as indicated by HbA1c levels, and the extent of macular thickening postoperatively. Patients with poorer glycemic control exhibited greater increases in macular thickness, particularly in the first week following surgery. This finding underscores the importance of maintaining good glycemic control in diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery to minimize

the risk of postoperative complications such as macular edema.

Visual acuity outcomes were positive, with all patients showing significant improvement in best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) by three months post-surgery. The improvement in visual acuity, regardless of changes in macular thickness, suggests that the transient increase in macular thickness does not have a long-term adverse effect on visual outcomes. The low incidence of clinically significant macular edema (CSME), which decreased over time, further supports the conclusion that uncomplicated cataract surgery is generally safe and effective for diabetic patients, provided that appropriate postoperative monitoring and glycemic control are maintained.

Overall, the study highlights the transient nature of macular thickening following cataract surgery in diabetic patients and emphasizes the critical role of glycemic management in minimizing postoperative complications. The overall positive visual acuity outcomes suggest that cataract surgery can be safely performed in diabetic patients, with careful attention to postoperative care and monitoring.

A study evaluated macular thickness alterations post-cataract surgery using OCT in diabetic patients. It found that 26% of individuals with diabetes experienced macular edema, with significant foveal thickness increases observed at the 6-week mark among patients with diabetic retinopathy compared to those without. The study highlights the correlation between macular thickness changes and HbA1C levels in diabetic patients [5].

A study compared macular thickness changes between diabetic patients without retinopathy and non-diabetic subjects post-uncomplicated phacoemulsification using Spectral Domain OCT. The study found an increase in retinal thickness in both groups up to six months after surgery, with no significant differences between diabetic and non-diabetic groups [6].

A study assessed macular thickness changes in diabetic versus non-diabetic patients' post-phacoemulsification. The results indicated significant increases in central foveal thickness at one-month post-surgery, with diabetic patients showing a higher incidence of macular edema [7].

A study explored the relationship between HbA1c levels and macular thickness in diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery. It found significant increases in macular thickness post-surgery, especially in patients with higher HbA1c levels, with more pronounced changes observed in those who underwent small incision cataract surgery (SICS) compared to phacoemulsification [8].

A study evaluated changes in macular status and choroidal thickness post-phacoemulsification in patients with mild to moderate non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR). It found that macular thickness and choroidal thickness significantly increased post-surgery, with greater increases observed in patients with NPDR compared to controls [9].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that uncomplicated cataract surgery in diabetic patients is associated with a transient increase in macular thickness, which generally resolves by 3 months postoperatively. The increase in macular thickness was correlated with poorer glycemic control, highlighting the importance of managing blood glucose levels in diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery. Visual acuity significantly improved postoperatively, indicating the overall success of the surgical intervention. The incidence of clinically significant macular edema was low, with most cases resolving within 3 months.

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